

Separating fast from slow cycling soil organic carbon – A multi-method comparison on land use change sites

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ABSTRACT

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is significantly affected by land use change (LUC). Consequently, LUC is a major controlling factor of total SOC contents and SOC pool dynamics. Several methods have been developed to assess distinct SOC pools, which includes particle size separation, thermal analysis and soil reflectance mid-infrared spectroscopy. All of which are considered to have a potential as high through put methods to generate large datasets. Here, we used 23 sites covering six different types of LUC to assess differences in fast and slow cycling SOC derived from three approaches. We used i) particle size fractionation to obtain coarse (>50 μm) and fine (<50 μm) SOC fractions; ii) thermal Rock-Eval® 6 analysis in compilation with the PARTY_{SOCV2.0EU} model to estimate active and stable SOC pools and iii) mid-infrared spectroscopy to determine the relative SOC composition and derive fast (aliphatic compounds) and slow (aromatic/carboxylic compounds) cycling SOC pools. The particle size SOC fractions and thermal SOC pools showed similar dynamics but differed substantially in the magnitude with LUC. The fine SOC fraction contained around two-thirds of the total SOC across all land uses and was strongly responsive by nearly matching the relative changes of total SOC (slope of 0.76 and $R^2 = 0.91$). Therefore, the fine fraction SOC might be more dynamic than considered until now. In comparison, the stable SOC pool calculated using PARTY_{SOCV2.0EU} was less responsive to the relative changes (slope of 0.43 and $R^2 = 0.72$) and contained around 40 % of the total SOC. This underlines that both physical and thermal approaches separate biogeochemically distinct pools. The qualitative assessment by mid-infrared spectroscopy related well to the thermal SOC pools but not to the particle size fractions. The initial land-use SOC composition, as a ratio of the corresponding fast and slow cycling SOC pool, can be a suitable predictor for SOC evolution. This was particularly true for thermal and mid-infrared spectroscopy derived SOC pools. We show that three conceptually different methods (physical, thermal and mid-infrared spectroscopic) are suitable to determine SOC pool changes for a large diversity of LUC, but the sensitivity of the individual pools can differ strongly, depending on the method.

1. Introduction

Land use change (LUC) is one of the strongest ecosystem disturbances and it affects soil organic carbon (SOC) by leading either to losses or gains in carbon and SOC quality (Guo and Gifford, 2002; Mueller and Koegel-Knabner, 2009; Poeplau et al., 2011; Wiesmeier et al., 2019). In general, LUC from less disturbed and partly managed systems such as forest or grassland to cultivated cropland results in losses of SOC, while the reverse can result in long-term gains (Guo and Gifford, 2002;

Poeplau and Don, 2013; Sanderman et al., 2017). The conversion of cropland to grassland and/or forest can result in SOC gains of up to 130% with a new equilibrium being reached within 100 years (Poeplau et al., 2011). The reverse conversion was found to result in losses of up to 40% with a new equilibrium generally occurring in less than 20 years in temperate climates (Poeplau et al., 2011). In consequence, croplands have, on average, lower SOC contents than grasslands (Drexler et al., 2022). On a global scale, it is estimated that 133 Pg C were lost from the upper two meters of soils with most of the losses occurring in the last 200

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years due to the conversion of natural land for agricultural use (Sanderman et al., 2017). This makes global LUC and land conversion a major source of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (IPCC, 2022).

Evaluating shifts in biogeochemical cycling of SOC upon LUC is crucial to understand and predict the overall dynamics of SOC and its subsequent climatic impact. At the same time, LUC can be used to evaluate the dynamic of specific isolated SOC pools towards disturbance and management shifts. The separation of SOC in fractions and pools is common to determine such biogeochemical properties of SOC. Clearly defined SOC pools that are comparable and consistent across land uses are further needed to improve SOC modelling and projections (Le Noë et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2016). To date, SOC models mostly fail to correctly capture LUC effects (Boysen et al., 2021; Gottschalk et al., 2010). Several methods have been developed to assess distinct SOC pools based on operational physical, chemical and thermal definitions (Plante et al., 2009; Poeplau et al., 2018). The responses of such defined SOC pools to LUC have rarely been studied comprehensively. Doing so is a straightforward way to reveal their biogeochemical relevance and conceptual definition regarding the drastic SOC changes associated with LUC.

Physical fractionation approaches are well established and separate the SOC in at least two pools consisting conceptually of particulate organic carbon and mineral associated organic carbon. The latter is considered to be a more stable SOC pool with generally longer turnover times of decades to centuries (Lavallee et al., 2020). Several operational definitions exist to separate the SOC by density and/or particle size. The separation solely by particle size (e.g. with thresholds between 50–20 μm) is proposed as an approach to separate distinct coarse and fine SOC fractions in a time and cost efficient manner (Just et al., 2021; Poeplau et al., 2018). The fractionation by particle size only results in two or more fractions. It is considered that the organic carbon in the coarse fraction ($\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$, e.g. $>50 \mu\text{m}$) is less protected and thus relatively fast cycling, while organic carbon in finer fractions (OC_{fine} , e.g. $<50 \mu\text{m}$) is considered to be dominated by mineral-protected organic carbon, by either occlusion or direct mineral association. The mineral-associated organic carbon fraction is gaining more and more attention for long-term carbon sequestration by increasing its carbon loading for SOC sequestration (Begill et al., 2023; Cotrufo et al., 2019; Georgiou et al., 2022). However, context- and management-dependent dynamics of SOC fractions are important to consider (Angst et al., 2023; Witzgall et al., 2021). Additionally, mineral-associated organic carbon is reported to contain substantial amounts of organic matter that might cycle on shorter timescales of months to years than the decadal or longer scales considered so far (Poeplau et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2022).

Thermal separation of SOC has been proposed to determine pools of varying biological stability (Krahl et al., 2023; Plante et al., 2009). The direct link of thermal and biological stability, however, has also been challenged (Dorodnikov et al., 2007; Schiedung et al., 2017). Rock-Eval® combines a ramped pyrolysis followed by thermal oxidation of the soil sample and receives increasing interest to distinguish different components of SOC according to their biogeochemical properties and relative turnover times in the soil (Barré et al., 2016; Disnar et al., 2003; Pacini et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2023). It has also been applied to large and national datasets (Delahaie et al., 2023) and assessments of soil organic matter quality and management in relation to ploughing practices (Deluz et al., 2024). Recently, Rock-Eval® analysis was further advanced with the machine-learning model PARTY_{SOC}V2.0_{EU} (Cécillon et al., 2021). This approach provides the separation of SOC into a relative stable pool cycling on centennial timescales and a faster cycling active pool.

Independent of the operational thresholds of physical and thermal fractionations, chemometric approaches by soil spectroscopy in the near- and mid-infrared range have become more established to estimate the chemical composition and functionality of organic matter in soils (Margenot et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 1991). Chemometric approaches were shown to predict SOC fractions and composition (Baldock et al.,

2018; Sanderman et al., 2021; Vos et al., 2018). Additionally, shifts within the mid-infrared spectral range aligned with SOC changes of long-term bare fallow experiment with diagnostic shifts in relation of aliphatic and aromatic/carboxylic bands that can be assigned to fast and slow cycling SOC pools (Demyan et al., 2012; Laub et al., 2020). However, a comprehensive comparison across physical, thermal and spectrometric methods, regarding their ability to isolate one stable and one labile pool is lacking.

Here we used 23 sites covering six different directions of LUC (i.e. forest to cropland, grassland to cropland, grassland to forest, cropland to grassland, cropland to forest and cropland to perennial *Miscanthus*). We used particle size fractionation to isolate organic carbon into $\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$ ($>50 \mu\text{m}$) and fine OC_{fine} ($<50 \mu\text{m}$) fractions (Begill et al., 2023). We applied Rock-Eval® analysis to estimate active ($\text{OC}_{\text{active}}$) and stable ($\text{OC}_{\text{stable}}$) SOC pools using the PARTY_{SOC}V2.0_{EU} (Cécillon et al., 2021). Additionally, we used mid-infrared spectroscopy (Diffusive Reflectance Infrared Fourier Transformed Spectroscopy (DRIFT-MIR)) to determine the relative SOC composition and relative peak areas of fast cycling (RPA_{fast}) and slow cycling (RPA_{slow}) SOC. We aim to evaluate the sensitivity of three distinct methods and advance on the biogeochemical meaning of the corresponding pools to determine SOC dynamics.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Land use change sites

Topsoils (0–10 cm) of 23 sites representing six LUC were included (Table S1). The LUC included three to five sites with a change from forest to cropland, grassland to forest, cropland to forest, grassland to cropland, cropland to grassland and cropland to perennial *Miscanthus*. On average, LUC occurred 39 ± 9 years before sampling, with a range of 3–160 years (Table 1). Most sites were located in temperate climate with $6.0 \pm 4.1^\circ\text{C}$ mean annual temperature (-3.4 to 13.0°C) and 756 mm mean annual precipitation (307 to 2415 mm) as averages of all sites. The forest to cropland sites were previously studied by Peplau et al. (2022) and Schroeder et al. (2022) and represented the most northern sites in the boreal zone of the Yukon Territory, Canada. Three of these sites (KL, MG and RC) were underlain by continuous permafrost and two sites (CD and LR) were not directly influenced by permafrost; and MAT ranged between -3.4 to 0.1°C . All other sites were located in the temperate zone, namely central Europe (Table S1). The cropland to *Miscanthus* sites were previously studied by Poeplau and Don (2014) and all other sites by Poeplau and Don (2013).

2.2. Particle size fractionation

All samples were fractionated by particle size into $\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$ (coarse fraction $>50 \mu\text{m}$) and OC_{fine} (fine fraction $<50 \mu\text{m}$) similar to Just et al. (2021) and Begill et al. (2023). In brief, 10 g of dried and $<2 \text{ mm}$ sieved soil was suspended in 150 ml of deionized water. The suspended samples were treated with ultrasonication using 100 J ml^{-1} (Sonifier 450-D with a high grain disrupter horn (diameter of 1.9 cm); Branson, USA)

Table 1

Overview and ranges of years since LUC, elevation, mean annual temperature (MAT), mean annual precipitation (MAP), pH, total soil organic carbon (SOC) and C:N ratios of all sites and current land uses. All samples are from the upper 0–10 cm from each site and all values are presented in Tables S1 and S2.

		Minimum	Average	Maximum
Years	[years]	3	39	160
Elevation	[m.a.s.l.]	6	371	1792
MAT	[$^\circ\text{C}$]	-3.4	6.0	13.0
MAP	[mm]	307	765	2415
pH	[$-$]	3.5	5.8	8.9
SOC	[g kg^{-1}]	8.29	36.08	162.21
C:N	[$-$]	9.73	14.38	30.91

followed by wet sieving. The fine fraction (<50 μm) was treated with 0.8 g $\text{CaCl}_2 \text{L}^{-1}$ and centrifuged for 15 min at 3800 g. Both fractions were dried at 60°C prior to milling and further analyses. The $\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$ and OC_{fine} are considered to represent free and fast cycling as well as mineral-associated and slow cycling SOC pools, respectively (Just et al., 2021). Bulk soil and fraction total organic carbon contents were determined using dry combustion (LECO Trumac; St. Joseph, USA). The average recovery of total mass was $98 \pm 1\%$ and the average recovery of organic carbon was $99 \pm 2\%$.

2.3. Thermal analysis with Rock-Eval® 6

Thermal analysis was performed using a Rock-Eval® 6 Turbo device (Vinci Technologies, France). Around 60 mg of ground and dried (40°C) samples were analyzed by pyrolysis and subsequent oxidation. For the pyrolysis phase the samples were in a N_2 atmosphere and treated for three minutes at 200°C followed by a temperature ramp from 200 to 650°C (rate of 30°C/min). Afterwards, an oxidation phase followed with one minute at 300°C followed by a temperature ramp from 300 to 850°C (20°C/min) with a five minutes isotherm at 850°C under laboratory air conditions. The Rock-Eval® analysis generates five thermograms with a resolution of one second. Three thermograms correspond to volatile hydrocarbon effluent, carbon monoxide (CO), and carbon dioxide (CO_2) that are measured during the pyrolysis phase and additional two thermograms correspond to CO and CO_2 measured during the oxidation phase.

Two kinetic SOC pools were predicted from the thermograms (pyrolysis and oxidation step) by using the $\text{PARTY}_{\text{SOCv2.0EU}}$ (Cécillon et al., 2021) implemented in the Geoworks software (Geoworks V1.6R2, Vinci Technologies, 2021). The $\text{PARTY}_{\text{SOCv2.0EU}}$ is calibrated with six European long-term bare fallow sites and predicts a centennial stable $\text{OC}_{\text{stable}}$ pool and a faster cycling $\text{OC}_{\text{active}}$ pool from bulk soils based on 18 parameters derived from the thermograms. Both pools are estimated as proportion of total SOC. To obtain the absolute $\text{OC}_{\text{active}}$ and $\text{OC}_{\text{stable}}$ (g C kg^{-1} soil), we multiplied the proportions with the total organic carbon obtained by dry combustion of bulk soils.

2.4. Mid-infrared spectroscopy

Milled and dried bulk soil samples were analyzed by mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopy to obtain compositional information of the SOC. Samples were packed in sample holders (13 mm in diameter) and the surface was flattened without compaction using a spatula. All spectra were acquired in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} using Diffusive Reflectance Infrared Fourier-Transformed (DRIFT-MIR) spectroscopy (Nicolet iS50 with a Collector II accessory, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Background reflectance was collected using roughened gold mirrors (Plasmagold, Pleiger Laseroptik, Germany) before each set of 20 samples. Background normalization and correction of CO_2 and H_2O interferences was performed using OMNIC (OMNIC, Version 9.13.1256, Thermo Fisher Scientific). For each sample, two replicates were scanned by co-adding 32 scans per replicates. All spectra were converted into absorption units as $\log(1/\text{reflectance})$. The replicate spectra were averaged per sample. All spectra were further processed using the *prospectr* (Stevens and Ramirez-Lopez, 2022) and *DescTools* (Signorelli, 2023) packages using the R (Version 4.3.0) environment R Studio (R Core Team, 2022). All spectra were trimmed to 4000–500 cm^{-1} and resampled at a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . A Savitzky-Golay smoothing with a window size of 9 cm^{-1} (Savitzky and Golay, 1964) was applied prior to a standard normal variate normalization. Peak areas of interest were determined by trimming the spectra to the peak corresponding range of wavenumbers and local baseline correction. Band ranges included 3010–2800 cm^{-1} for aliphatic C-H (anti)symmetric stretches and 1660–1580 cm^{-1} for aromatic C=C and carboxylic C=O stretches (Demyan et al., 2012). The ratio of peak areas of fast cycling aliphatic and slow cycling aromatic/carboxylic compounds was used to calculate

the DRIFT-MIR Stability Index (DSI) as presented by Laub et al. (2020). The band range at 3010–2800 cm^{-1} is free of mineral phase interferences in the absorbance (Margenot et al., 2023) and allows the comparison of organic matter composition between soils of different texture. Bands at 1660–1580 cm^{-1} can be overlaid by absorbance of quartz and Si-O-Si, which would require additional pre-treatment such as spectral subtraction of the pure mineral phase spectrum (Reeves, 2012). However, we compare here pairs of adjacent LUC sites that are similar in texture and thus all changes in peak area can be assigned to shifts in the aromatic C=C and carboxylic C=O stretches. Additionally to texture interferences, organic matter and interactions with Ca^{2+} in alkaline soils can increase absorbances at regions around 1620 cm^{-1} , which can lead to an overestimation of aromatic compounds (Ellerbrock and Gerke, 2021). For each compound, the relative peak area (RPA) was calculated by dividing it by the sum of total peak areas of all compounds. We considered the RPA of aliphatic compounds to represent a fast-cycling SOC pool (RPA_{fast}) and the RPA of aromatic/carboxylic as a slow-cycling SOC pool (RPA_{slow}), following the same interpretation made in other studies (Demyan et al., 2012; Fissore et al., 2017; Laub et al., 2020; Mainka et al., 2022; Ryals et al., 2014; Schiedung et al., 2022; Wasner et al., 2024). Compared to the particle size and thermal analysis, the DRIFT-MIR derived pools represent relative composition and cannot be directly related to amounts of SOC.

2.5. Calculations and statistics

Absolute changes of organic carbon (*absolute* ΔOC) of bulk soil, particle fractions and thermal pools in g OC kg^{-1} soil were calculated as:

$$\text{absolute}\Delta\text{OC} = \text{OC}_{\text{LU2}} - \text{OC}_{\text{LU1}}$$

Where OC_{LU1} is the organic carbon content of the initial land use and OC_{LU2} the organic carbon content of the new land use. Accordingly, relative changes in organic carbon *relative* ΔOC were calculated as:

$$\text{relative}\Delta\text{OC} = \frac{\text{OC}_{\text{LU2}} - \text{OC}_{\text{LU1}}}{\text{OC}_{\text{LU1}}} \times 100$$

Similarly, relative changes in DSI and RPA were calculated.

All statistical analyses were performed using R (Version 4.3.0). All values are presented with the standard error of the mean, if not stated differently. Two-samples Wilcoxon tests were used to test for significant differences between total SOC and fraction/pool within the particle size fractions and $\text{PARTY}_{\text{SOCv2.0EU}}$ SOC pools for each direction of LUC. Non-parametric ranked analysis of similarities (ANOSIM) between the particle size and the SOC pools extracted using $\text{PARTY}_{\text{SOCv2.0EU}}$ (i.e. coarse vs. active and fine vs. stable) was applied using the *vegan* package.

3. Results

3.1. Soil organic carbon changes with land use change

The conversion from forest and permanent grassland to cropland consistently resulted in significant SOC losses ($p < 0.001$; Fig. 1a and b). The conversion from grassland to forest did not result in significant changes of SOC contents, due to only small decreases of two sites and increases in SOC at one site (Fig. 1c). When cropland was converted to forest, grassland or permanent *Miscanthus* land use, bulk SOC contents increased significantly (Fig. 1d, e and f).

3.2. Separated soil organic carbon pools

Across all soils and land uses, 6.69–49.05 g SOC kg^{-1} were on average stored as OC_{fine} (0.93–123.49 g SOC kg^{-1} as $\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$; Fig. 2), which corresponds to $74 \pm 3\%$ (range 24–94%) of total SOC (Fig. 3). The relative proportion of OC_{fine} was highest in cropland soils that generally

Fig. 1. Changes in soil organic carbon contents with LUC. All individual sites are indicated by symbols for each LUC. The blue dots and lines represent the average change with standard error of the mean. The p-values (two-sampled Wilcoxon test) indicate the level of significance of the soil organic carbon content difference between land uses. More site information is presented in Table S1.

contained less total SOC compared to all other land uses. The forest to cropland sites that are underlain by sporadic permafrost showed a higher proportion of OC_{coarse} compared to the OC_{fine} .

The OC_{stable} pool, determined by the PARTY_{SOC}v2.0_{EU} model using Rock-Eval® results as input variables, contributed on average to $41 \pm 2\%$ (range 25–73%) of the total SOC. Thus, the majority ($59 \pm 2\%$) of the SOC was in the OC_{active} pool across all land uses (Fig. 3). Therefore, $2.92\text{--}121.77 \text{ g SOC kg}^{-1}$ were in the OC_{active} pool across all land uses and in OC_{stable} $4.20\text{--}40.44 \text{ g SOC kg}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2).

3.3. Changes in bulk soil and organic carbon pools

The changes of organic carbon in the particle size fractions and pools determined by PARTY_{SOC}v2.0_{EU} analysis were generally highly correlated with changes of bulk SOC ($R^2 > 0.7$, Fig. 4a and b and Table 2). The relative changes were larger for the OC_{coarse} and the OC_{active} pool compared to OC_{fine} and OC_{stable} pool, respectively. The relative change of OC_{fine} was very similar to the relative total SOC change (slope of 0.77, Fig. 4a and Table 2). In comparison, the relative change of OC_{stable} was weaker (slope of 0.43, Fig. 4b and Table 2).

Absolute changes in SOC content correlated well with changes of OC_{active} and OC_{stable} pool ($R^2 > 0.91$) across all LUC (Fig. S1). The change of OC_{active} contents (slope of 0.78) was stronger than of the OC_{stable} pool (slope of 0.23). The absolute changes in the particle size fractions were strongly influenced by the forest to cropland LUC (Fig. S1 and S2). Excluding the forest to cropland sites, the absolute changes of OC_{fine}

contents represented well the SOC content changes ($R^2 = 0.98$) with strong responses (slope of 0.75, Fig. S2).

The semiquantitative assessment by DRIFT-MIR showed a clear increase in RPA_{fast} , representing aliphatic bands, with relative increasing SOC contents (Fig. 4c and Table 2). The RPA_{slow} decreased accordingly with relative increases in SOC contents and increased when SOC decreased.

3.4. Relationship between organic carbon pools and SOC changes

The DRIFT-MIR stability index (DSI) did not show a relationship with the ratio of $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$ particle size fraction but did have a positive correlation with the ratio of $OC_{active}:OC_{stable}$ (Fig. 5a and b). The relationship between $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$ and $OC_{active}:OC_{stable}$ was weak ($R^2 = 0.12$) and driven by forest sites (Fig. 5c).

Higher $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$ and $OC_{active}:OC_{stable}$ ratios and DSI (all meaning a larger proportion of corresponding fast cycling SOC pool) of the initial land use related to larger SOC losses (Fig. 6). Vice versa, lower composition ratios (i.e. larger proportion of the corresponding slow cycling SOC pool) of the initial land use resulted in larger gains of SOC with LUC. Such relationships were best explained by the $OC_{active}:OC_{stable}$ ratios ($R^2 = 0.49$), followed by the DSI ($R^2 = 0.20$) and $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$ ratio ($R^2 = 0.19$). The latter was highly influenced by the forest to cropland LUC that had high initial ratios. Excluding the forest to cropland LUC resulted in no clear relationship between initial $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$ ratio and SOC changes ($R^2 = 0.08$; $p = 0.13$) but did only slightly alter the

Fig. 2. Absolute soil organic carbon content of particle fractions ($\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$ and OC_{fine}) and pools estimated with PARTY_{SOCv2.0EU} ($\text{OC}_{\text{active}}$ and $\text{OC}_{\text{stable}}$) for the different types of LUC (a-f). For each panel, the land use on the left represents the initial and, on the right, the new land use after change. Error bars indicate the error of the mean of all LUC of $n = 3$ to $n = 5$ (Table S1). Note differences in y-axes scaling. Significant differences between the SOC of particle size fractions and the SOC pools extracted by PARTY_{SOCv2.0EU} are presented in Table S3.

linear relationship for DSI and $\text{OC}_{\text{active}}:\text{OC}_{\text{stable}}$ ratio (Fig. S3).

4. Discussion

The overall SOC changes (Fig. 1) confirm the general observed decreases in SOC contents after conversion from forest and grassland to cropland. The SOC contents increased when croplands were converted to grasslands, forests or perennial *Miscanthus* cultivation (Peplau et al., 2022; Poepplau and Don, 2014, 2013). The SOC fractions extracted by particle size and SOC pools determined with PARTY_{SOCv2.0EU} followed the same direction of change with the corresponding LUC (Figs. 2 and 3). However, the magnitude differed between the two approaches, which indicates their different responsivity.

4.1. Responses of $\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$ and OC_{fine}

The changes in the particle size fractions correspond to previous findings and with highest proportions of particulate organic carbon (here $\text{OC}_{\text{coarse}}$) found in forest soils followed by grasslands and croplands on European and global scale (Hansen et al., 2024; Lugato, 2021). Additionally, grasslands are reported to contain twice or more particulate organic carbon compared to managed croplands due to the larger input of the permanent vegetation cover and larger root inputs (Christensen, 2001; Poepplau and Don, 2013). Across all land-uses, the OC_{fine} represented two-thirds of the total SOC. Therefore, the OC_{fine}

comprised nearly twice the amount of SOC recovered in the $\text{OC}_{\text{stable}}$ pool that was determined by PARTY_{SOCv2.0EU} (Fig. 3). In consequence, the absolute SOC changes along the sequence of LUC, were dominated by the responses of the OC_{fine} (Fig. 4a and S1). This indicates that the fine particle size fraction might isolate a proportion of SOC that is relatively similar to the bulk soil in terms of its kinetic dynamics. At least in agricultural soils, OC_{fine} and mineral associated carbon in fact resembles the major proportion of total SOC (Begill et al., 2023; Delahaie et al., 2024; Georgiou et al., 2022; Soinnie et al., 2024). The responses found here underline that OC_{fine} and mineral associated organic carbon can consist of organic matter that has a shorter residence time of suggested several decades to centuries (Kleber et al., 2015; von Lützwow et al., 2007). In the present study the LUC occurred on average of all sites 38 ± 9 years ago (range of 3–160 years; Table S1) and thus on a shorter timescale than major changes of the OC_{fine} would be expected. In fact, the coarse and fine SOC fractions are known to both contain short-term cycling organic matter with similar composition (Yu et al., 2022), which can partly be associated to pathways of rapid and direct mineral association of organic matter (Cotrufo et al., 2015). Further, physical fractions can be affected by methodological cross-contamination (Lavalley et al., 2020).

Here we used a separation by particle size only and no separation of light particulate organic matter by density. Leuthold et al. (2024) compared the qualitative composition of particle and density fractions and its combination and reported that the mineral associated fractions

Fig. 3. Proportion of soil organic carbon in particle fractions (OC_{coarse} and OC_{fine}) and pools estimated with $PARTY_{\text{SOCV2.0EU}}$ (OC_{active} and OC_{stable}) for the different LUC (a-f). For each panel, the land use on the left represents the initial and, on the right, the new land use after change. Error bars indicate the error of the mean of all LUC of $n = 3$ to $n = 5$ (Table S1). Significant differences between the SOC of particle size fractions and the SOC pools extracted by $PARTY_{\text{SOCV2.0EU}}$ are presented in Table S3.

were similar in terms of its composition. The particulate organic matter fractions, however, were reported to show a larger variability with potential contamination with the mineral phase when separating by particle size only. We performed additional analysis of the particle size fractions using DRIFT-MIR and applying principal component analysis in the present study. This showed that the OC_{fine} , that contained the largest proportion of the total SOC, was more similar to the bulk soil spectra than OC_{coarse} . The spectra of the OC_{coarse} , in comparison, were more different from the bulk SOC and OC_{fine} spectra (Fig. S4). Here, the mineralogy (i.e. quartz and kaolinite associated bands) and the abundance of aromatic compounds were decisive for differences between the fraction (Fig. S5). This is a consequence of the size separation at a threshold value of $50 \mu\text{m}$, resulting in the dominance of quartz but it could also indicate the potential abundance of stable aggregates and pyrogenic organic matter in the OC_{coarse} fraction.

The OC_{fine} might have a faster turnover than previously thought, which is supported by other studies. For example, in a two-year incubation experiment, using isotopically labelled organic matter, Poelau et al. (2023) found the native OC_{fine} to be depleted by 20%. One reason for this might be the heterogeneous nature of that fraction. This is

caused by the fact that size fractionation does always lead to some degree of contamination of the OC_{fine} fraction with fine and not mineral associated organic matter particles. However, it is also possible that not everything that is considered a mineral association leads to a long-term stabilization of carbon. For example, adsorbed organic carbon can be desorbed by phosphate when land management changes, which makes stabilized SOC available for microbial mineralization (Spohn et al., 2022). Additionally, a substantial proportion of mineral associated carbon can be directly root derived that might be faster cycling and more dynamic than organic matter that was stabilized by *in vivo* pathways through microbial decomposition (Schiedung et al., 2023b; Sokol et al., 2019). Fungal hyphae or other types of microbial debris on the outside of micro-aggregates might be relatively unprotected and thus rather labile (Witzgall et al., 2021). A potential faster cycling of mineral associated carbon was also reported from long-term bare fallow experiments by Lutfalla et al. (2019), who reported declining carbon contents of clay size fractions within a few decades. The responses to LUC found in this study imply that the OC_{fine} can contain a substantial amount of faster cycling organic matter. Thus, the long-term protection of SOC against mineralization and stabilization of SOC in this fraction and

Fig. 4. Relative change of organic carbon content in particle fraction (a, OC_{coarse} and OC_{fine}) and pools estimated with $PARTY_{SOCv2.0_{EU}}$ (b, OC_{active} and OC_{stable}) with relative change of total bulk soil organic carbon for each LUC. In (c) the relative change in the relative peak area of the fast (RPA_{fast}) and slow (RPA_{slow}) SOC pool determined by DRIFT-MIR with the relative change of total SOC for each LUC is shown. Linear regressions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Linear regressions fitted for relative SOC content changes of SOC fraction/pool and relative peak areas (RPA) obtained from DRIFT-MIR with relative bulk SOC content changes as shown in Fig. 4. The relative change describes the difference between initial land use and new land use. All linear model fits were determined with an intercept at the coordinated origin, since no SOC content change cannot result in SOC pool changes.

SOC pool/fraction	Estimate	Std. Error	Adj. R^2	t	p-value
ΔOC_{coarse}	2.15	0.16	0.89	13.7	<0.001
ΔOC_{fine}	0.76	0.05	0.91	15.6	<0.001
ΔOC_{active}	1.64	0.08	0.95	21.5	<0.001
ΔOC_{stable}	0.43	0.06	0.72	7.7	<0.001
ΔRPA_{fast}	0.26	0.03	0.77	8.7	<0.001
ΔRPA_{slow}	-0.40	0.08	0.50	-4.9	<0.001

comparable mineral associated organic carbon fractions might have been overestimated to some extent.

4.2. Responses of OC_{active} and OC_{stable}

The determination of OC_{active} and OC_{stable} pools by $PARTY_{SOCv2.0_{EU}}$ was generally sensitive to SOC changes with LUC (Figs. 3 and 4). Comparison of OC_{active} and OC_{stable} pools with a wide range of results is limited given the low number of published studies. However, for seven French long-term experiments including 29 management treatments, Kanari et al. (2022) reported that 59% of the SOC (range 44–74% of SOC) were in the OC_{stable} pool, which is comparable to the croplands in this study. Delahaie et al. (2024) investigated 2,037 sites of the French soil inventory (RMQS) using $PARTY_{SOCv2.0_{EU}}$ and reported that 65%, 62% and 48% of total SOC were in the OC_{active} pool for forest, grasslands

Fig. 5. Correlation between DRIFT-MIR stability index (DSI) with $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$ particle fraction ratio (a) and $OC_{active}:OC_{stable}$ pool ratio (b) and the correlation between the two fraction ratios (c) for each current land use. All with a linear fit.

Fig. 6. Relationship between the relative SOC change and DRIFT-MIR stability index (DSI), the ratios of $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$ fractions and $OC_{active}:OC_{stable}$ pool of the initial land use. The symbols represent each direction of land use change.

and croplands, respectively. This is comparable to the proportions found in this study, which results in proportion of OC_{active} on total SOC of $65 \pm 3\%$ in forest, $68 \pm 2\%$ grassland, $58 \pm 7\%$ *Miscanthus* and $50 \pm 3\%$ in cropland soils (Fig. 3). Similar to our findings, Delahaie et al. (2024) reported a larger proportion of mineral associated carbon and smaller proportion of particulate organic carbon within the French soil inventory compared to the OC_{stable} and OC_{active} pool. In the present study, the OC_{active} was dominating the total SOC changes of the LUC (Fig. 4b). In fact, the absolute change of OC_{active} along the bulk SOC changes was similar to the OC_{fine} of the particle size fractionation (when excluding the forest to cropland sites under permafrost) with a slope of 0.77 and 0.75 of the linear regression (Fig. S1 and S2), respectively. This corresponds to the definition of the OC_{active} pool with turnover times of a few decades (Cécillon et al., 2021; Kanari et al., 2022). In comparison, the OC_{stable} pool is defined as a centennially cycling pool (Cécillon et al., 2021). Therefore, our study, covering a large gradient of LUC and SOC changes, serves as a proof of concept for the OC_{active} and OC_{stable} pools of the PARTY_{SOCv2.0EU} method to be relatively insensitive to perturbations, more than it did for the particle size fractionation.

4.3. The responses of MIR pools

The qualitative assessment of the SOC pools by DRIFT-MIR was suitable to determine shifts in SOC composition with LUC and associated SOC changes (Fig. 4c). With the direction of LUC that resulted in an increase in SOC, the relative contribution of fast cycling SOC (RPA_{fast}) increased. Decreasing SOC resulted in a relative enrichment of the slow cycling pool (RPA_{slow}). The strong and clear responses of the RPA_{fast} and RPA_{slow} in this study (Figs. 4 and 6), illustrate that SOC compositional derived information can explain mechanisms of SOC dynamics. The increase in RPA_{fast} with increasing SOC after LUC can be assigned to directly plant-derived organic matter that accumulates when croplands are converted to grasslands, *Miscanthus* cultivation and forest (Fig. 4). On the trajectory of shifts towards declining SOC contents, due to the conversion of forest and grasslands to cropland, the increases in RPA_{slow} point towards the accumulation of processed organic matter in cropland soils. This is in line with the conceptual understanding of fast utilization of plant-derived organic matter in cropland soils due to faster

mineralization rates and the accumulation of plant-derived organic matter in grassland and forest soils. This underlines the promising link of directly extracted DRIFT-MIR spectra information (e.g. RPA and DSI) with SOC dynamics.

Important for direct comparison of spectra between soils is the soil matrix effect and absorbance interferences that challenge the extraction of SOC qualitative information (Margenot et al., 2023). For example, cation interaction (e.g. Ca) of organic matter can alter the peak intensity and location in the MIR spectra due to shifts in the extinction coefficient (Ellerbrock and Gerke, 2021). With higher Ca^{2+} content, e.g. increasing pH, the peak intensity of aromatic compounds (C=C and C=C bonds at around 1620 cm^{-1}) can be increased to a much larger extent than aliphatic bond (C-H at around 2930 cm^{-1}), which can bias the interpretation when pH changes between land uses are present. We included sites with alkaline pH (Table 1 and S2). However, the changes between the individual pairs of LUC from alkaline to neutral or slightly acidic occurred only at the cropland to forest sites. We could not identify that the RPA of the aromatic compounds were substantially affected by a Ca^{2+} co-absorption and shifts in the spectra. The cropland to forest LUC sites aligned well with the remaining data set and observed RPA trends (Figs. 4c and 5). Our results show that the assessment of RPA_{fast} and RPA_{slow} is suitable to identify the LUC induced changes in SOC quality. However, the effects of the soil matrix are important to consider for future research. Especially, when such approaches are applied to sample sets that do not include the comparison of the same soil and texture as done here with the LUC pairs with similar matrix effects.

4.4. Link between SOC pools

The weak relationship between the relative composition of particle size fractions (ratio of $OC_{coarse}:OC_{fine}$) and the SOC pools derived from PARTY_{SOCv2.0EU} (ratio of $OC_{active}:OC_{stable}$) and DRIFT-MIR (DSI) indicate the different nature and biogeochemical role of these pools (Fig. 5). Similarly, Delahaie et al. (2024) concluded that particle size fractionation and thermal analysis result in different but complementary separation of SOC for which its biogeochemical dynamic depends on distinct pedogenic and climatic factors. On the French national scale, Delahaie et al. (2024) found that OC_{stable} and the SOC in the fine particle fraction were mainly driven by pedogenic factors (e.g. Fe oxy/hydroxides and exchangeable cations) while OC_{active} was mainly influenced by climatic factors. The SOC in the coarse particle size fraction was largely depending on land cover. Therefore, both approaches can add valuable information to understand SOC dynamics.

The methodological discrepancies observed for the forest to cropland LUC underlain by permafrost indicated that particle size fractionation can overestimate the fraction of fast cycling organic matter by solely relying on physical properties. Including the forest to cropland LUC sites decreased the linear regression for changes in OC_{fine} and total SOC ($y=0.23x$; $R^2=0.33$; $p<0.01$) and increased the regression performance for OC_{coarse} ($y=0.77x$, $R^2=0.85$; $p<0.001$; Fig. S2). The OC_{active} and OC_{stable} determined by PARTY_{SOCv2.0EU}, were more robust and the changes of organic carbon content aligned well with the total SOC changes (Fig. S1). The forest to cropland sites included here are located in permafrost regions of northern Canada (Peplau et al., 2022; Schroeder et al., 2022) and can be seen as specific ecosystems that can be considered pedo-climatic outliers. It is possible that these sites might have been affected by a larger fraction of particulate organic matter at the forest sites that originated rather from the forest floor than being part of the mineral soil. This can be attributed to the general challenge to determine the clear boundary between forest floor and the underlain mineral soils. Additionally, boreal forest systems are prone to wildfire. It is reported that $6.9 \pm 0.5\%$ of SOC in north Canadian forest mineral soils can be pyrogenic carbon (Schiedung et al., 2024), which is generally more persistent to environmental degradation than non-pyrogenic organic matter (Bird et al., 2015; Schiedung et al., 2023a). The potential artefact of organic layer sampling and a potential pyrogenic carbon

source might have had a strong impact on the particle size fractionation, containing $65 \pm 11\%$ of the SOC as OC_{coarse} at these specific forest sites (Figs. 2 and 3). Additionally, the OC_{coarse} decreased substantially in the croplands ($59.3 \pm 18.6 \text{ g OC kg}^{-1}$ soil for forest and $17.3 \pm 4.2 \text{ g OC kg}^{-1}$ soil in cropland; Fig. 2a), which might also be attributed to a dilution of particulate organic matter when the forest soils are ploughed for cropping and topsoil is mixed with SOC depleted deeper soil. We analyzed the upper 0–10 cm and thus cannot directly capture a depth transfer of coarse material by ploughing.

The relationship between the $PARTY_{\text{SOCV2.0EU}}$ pools and the qualitative SOC assessment by DRIFT-MIR was much stronger (Fig. 5b). The $PARTY_{\text{SOCV2.0EU}}$ is trained on bare fallow experiments to determine the OC_{active} and OC_{stable} pools (Cécillon et al., 2021). The RPA_{fast} and RPA_{slow} were also suitable to improve modelling of turnover times in long-term bare fallow experiments (Laub et al., 2020), to assess SOC quality change with long-term management (Demyan et al., 2012) or to determine SOC quality in major soil types in the Czech Republic (Pavlu et al., 2023). Therefore, RockEval® and MIR spectroscopy-based approaches seem to cover conceptually similar SOC pools. The thermal analysis and also DRIFT-MIR analysis consider the energetic status (i.e., defined by thermal stability) of the organic matter and its chemical composition but do not rely directly on physical properties such as particle size. Therefore, they might be more suitable to capture SOC stability properties that is partially controlled by the inherent resistance or recalcitrance (e.g., lignin containing plant debris in forest floors) rather than solely by its stabilization within the soil or integrate the combination of SOC stabilizing factors resulting in its long-term retention. Therefore, they can add valuable information of SOC pool models.

4.5. Initial composition to determine SOC evolution

The initial SOC fraction and pool distribution, as ratios of methods corresponding to fast:slow cycling SOC pools, aligned well with the total SOC changes with LUC (Fig. 6). In general, the losses of SOC were largest when the initial land use had a higher ratio and consequently contained a larger proportion of fast cycling SOC (e.g. OC_{coarse} , OC_{active} and larger $RPA_{\text{aliphatic}}$). Conversely, the gains of SOC were stronger when the initial land use had a lower ratio of the SOC fraction/pools and was dominated by slow cycling SOC (e.g. OC_{fine} , OC_{stable} and larger RPA_{aromatic}). Luo et al. (2020) reported that the initial pool size of particulate and mineral associated organic matter was the best predictor to determine SOC dynamics in 176 trials of LUC in Australia. This effect is also known as the “baseline effect”, meaning that the initial SOC composition prior to a change can be an indicator for SOC evolution and can support SOC management considerations. Our findings show that the detection of the “baseline effect” differed between the three methods. The strongest relationship with SOC changes was given for the initial $OC_{\text{active}}:OC_{\text{stable}}$ pool composition followed by the DSI (Fig. 6). The initial $OC_{\text{coarse}}:OC_{\text{fine}}$ ratio indicated also a good relationship when all sites are included. However, this relationship was not given any more when excluding the forest to cropland sites that contained larger fractions of OC_{coarse} as discussed before (Fig. S3). This underlines that the particulate SOC (e.g. OC_{coarse}), which is separated by size, might not always be sensitive enough to serve as an early indicator of SOC changes (Leifeld and Kögel-Knabner, 2005). These missing dynamics of the OC_{coarse} and the dominance of the OC_{fine} to represent total SOC challenge the use of particle size fractions to determine vulnerability of SOC to LUC and management changes. Thermal and chemometric approaches, that integrate stabilization and composition of SOC, may be more suitable approaches to project potential directions and magnitudes of SOC changes with LUC. Therefore, these approaches could be a valuable step to identify indicators for SOC vulnerability (e.g. highly sensitive to LUC or climatic changes) for region-specific strategies based on SOC models in combination with larger inventories (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2019). However, an important advantage of classical physical fractionation approaches is that tracing methods such as stable isotopes and radiocarbon analysis

can be used to more directly study the pathways of carbon stabilization in the soil (Balesdent et al., 1987; Trumbore, 2009).

5. Conclusion

Our research underlines that three distinct approaches to determine SOC cycling and composition can help to predict the magnitude of SOC change after LUC. However, the proportions of individual SOC fractions/pools and their sensitivity to LUC differed between methods. The changes in particle size based SOC fractions were dominated by OC_{fine} , which represents most of the SOC and indicates that this fraction is highly dynamic. We therefore suggest to consider it as a somewhat stabilized, yet not persistent fraction of total SOC. Using thermal separation of OC_{active} and OC_{stable} pools, as calculated using $PARTY_{\text{SOCV2.0EU}}$, indicated a higher sensitivity of OC_{active} to LUC, which aligns with the concept of the method. However, particle size fractionation and thermal RockEval® analyses indicated similar directions of change with LUC and thus they can be complementary while representing different biogeochemically relevant SOC pools. The determination of SOC composition by DRIFT-MIR spectroscopy can be a strong addition to determine SOC dynamics. The link between initial SOC composition and overall SOC changes could have important implications for determining directions and magnitudes of SOC changes and for identifying SOC vulnerability. This relationship was clearer for SOC pools derived from $PARTY_{\text{SOCV2.0EU}}$ and the DRIFT-MIR assessment, which could be used for baselines and indicators of SOC and soil management advice or initializing SOC models.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marcus Schiedung: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pierre Barré:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Christopher Peoplau:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2024.117154>.

Data availability

All data is available on request and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14527915>.

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